

ARRAY CALIBRATION IN THE PRESENCE OF UNKNOWN SENSOR CHARACTERISTICS AND MUTUAL COUPLING

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a method that is capable of handling simultaneously gain, phase and location as well as mutual coupling uncertainties is proposed for calibrating a planar array of general geometry. The proposed technique assumes that the array gain and phase errors are non-directional and that three time-disjoint pilot sources are available. The efficiency and the potential benefits of the proposed pilot calibration method are illustrated by a number of representative examples.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well known that signal subspace techniques are based on the a priori knowledge of the geometrical (location) and electrical (gain and phase) sensor characteristics, which is assumed to be accurate. Nevertheless, in practice, this assumption is often not satisfied due to perturbations in the array characteristics.

Indeed, uncertainties associated with the location of the sensors may differentiate the array geometrical structure from the assumed one, whereas multiple factors of static (e.g. ageing) or dynamic nature (e.g. environmental conditions) can cause gain as well as phase fluctuations.

These uncertainties, or changes, simultaneously affect mutual coupling between the array elements, which occurs when nominally passive sensors act as transmitters and re-radiate a part of the impinging signals' energy. In these terms, if mutual coupling effects are present in an array system, it is fallacious either to ignore them or quantify their impact based on nominal sensor properties and initial measurements [1-3].

As a matter of fact, the performance of signal subspace techniques is severely degraded in cases of errors in the array and mutual coupling modelling. Hence, various approaches have been presented in the past in order to identify these errors and rectify our knowledge of the actual sensor characteristics, that is calibrate the array. However, previous attempts to address the calibration problem either do not take the mutual coupling effects into account or require a large number of transmitting sources and, in the case of self-

calibration techniques, involve a significant convergence burden [4-8].

Therefore, in this paper a pilot method is proposed for the calibration of planar arrays of general geometry. Errors in the geometrical and electrical array characteristics as well as in the mutual coupling modelling are simultaneously considered. The proposed calibration technique assumes that the electrical errors are direction-independent, employs an analytical model for the mutual coupling effects and requires the use of three time-disjoint pilot sources. Since the required sources are time-disjoint, it is implicit that only one pilot source may be used from three distinct locations.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. In Section 2, the modelling of the array data covariance matrix in the presence of mutual coupling is presented. In Section 3, the proposed calibration method is described in detail and then, in Section 4, its performance is demonstrated by some representative examples. Finally, the paper is concluded in Section 5.

2 MODELLING OF THE ARRAY DATA COVARIANCE MATRIX

Consider an array of N sensors that operates in the presence of one pilot source of power normalised to unity. In the absence of mutual coupling, the array data covariance matrix $\mathbb{R}_{xx}$ is expressed as:

$$\mathbb{R}_{xx} = \underline{S} \cdot \underline{S}^H + \sigma^2 \mathbb{I}_N \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{S}$ is the so-called manifold or source position vector (SPV) and σ^2 is the power of noise, assumed to be isotropic and uncorrelated from sensor to sensor. Note that if noise is not isotropic, but has known statistics, it can be transformed to appear isotropic by preprocessing the array data samples.

In the case of the source being placed in the array far-field at azimuth θ and elevation angle ϕ with respect to the array reference point, that is by assuming plane-wave propagation, the SPV can be modelled as follows:

$$\underline{S} = \underline{\gamma} \odot \exp(j\phi) \odot \exp(-j\underline{r}^T \underline{k}) \quad (2)$$

where $\underline{\gamma} = [\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_N]^T$, $\phi = [\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_N]^T$ and $\underline{r} = [r_1, r_2, \dots, r_N] = [r_x, r_y, r_z]^T$. The parameters γ_i , ϕ_i and r_i , for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, represent respectively the gain, phase and location (in $\frac{\lambda}{2}$, where λ is the source's wavelength) characteristics of the i^{th} sensor, while

$\underline{k} = \pi[\cos\theta\cos\phi, \sin\theta\cos\phi, \sin\phi]^T$ is the vector that points towards the direction of the pilot source and $\odot$ denotes the Hadamard product.

In practical cases, the knowledge of the sensor characteristics γ , ϕ and $\underline{r}$ in Equation (2) is often not complete. In other words, if $\hat{\gamma}$, $\hat{\phi}$, $\hat{\underline{r}}$ are the nominal (known) characteristics and $\tilde{\gamma}$, $\tilde{\phi}$, $\tilde{\underline{r}}$ their respective perturbations, the true array characteristics will be given by $\underline{\gamma} = \hat{\gamma} + \tilde{\gamma}$, $\underline{\phi} = \hat{\phi} + \tilde{\phi}$ and $\underline{r} = \hat{\underline{r}} + \tilde{\underline{r}}$. Therefore, the true SPV will be expressed as $\underline{S} = \hat{\underline{S}} + \tilde{\underline{S}}$.

In the presence of mutual coupling however, the modelling of Equation (2) is also affected by the so-called mutual coupling matrix (MCM) $\mathbb{C}$ (i.e. $\mathbb{C} \cdot \underline{S}$). As a consequence, the array data covariance matrix is expressed as:

$$\mathbb{R}_{xx} = \mathbb{C} \cdot \underline{S} \cdot \underline{S}^H \cdot \mathbb{C}^H + \sigma^2 \mathbb{I}_N \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbb{C}$ modelled, according to [1], as:

$$\mathbb{C} = \mathbb{A} \odot \mathbb{L} \odot \mathbb{G} \odot \exp(j\Psi) \odot \exp(j\pi\mathbb{D}) \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathbb{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{1-a'_1} & \sqrt{a_2} & \dots & \sqrt{a_N} \\ \sqrt{a_1} & \sqrt{1-a'_2} & \dots & \sqrt{a_N} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sqrt{a_1} & \sqrt{a_2} & \dots & \sqrt{1-a'_N} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbb{L} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & l_{12} & \dots & l_{1N} \\ l_{21} & 1 & \dots & l_{2N} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ l_{N1} & l_{N2} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbb{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & g_{12} & \dots & g_{1N} \\ g_{21} & 1 & \dots & g_{2N} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ g_{N1} & g_{N2} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Psi = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \psi_2 & \dots & \psi_N \\ \psi_1 & 0 & \dots & \psi_N \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \psi_1 & \psi_2 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbb{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & d_{12} & \dots & d_{1N} \\ d_{21} & 1 & \dots & d_{2N} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ d_{N1} & d_{N2} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

In the above, a'_i is the power dissipated by the i^{th} sensor, a_i is the power of its re-radiated signal to the other sensors and ψ_i is the phase introduced to this signal. Furthermore, for $i, k = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $i \neq k$, $l_{ik} = \frac{1}{2\pi d_{ik}}$, $g_{ik} = \gamma_i \gamma_k \cdot \exp(j(\phi_i + \phi_k))$ and $d_{ik} = \|\underline{r}_i - \underline{r}_k\|$. In these terms, the MCM depends on:

- the rms values of both the directly received and the re-radiated signals ($\mathbb{A}$)
- the free space propagation losses ($\mathbb{L}$)
- the electrical sensor characteristics ($\mathbb{G}$)
- the phases introduced to the re-radiated signals (Ψ)
- the sensor locations ($\mathbb{D}$)

Again, in the presence of geometrical and electrical array uncertainties there will be a known (nominal) and an unknown (perturbation) value in all the matrix parameters $\mathbb{P}$ involved in Equation (4) (i.e. $\mathbb{P} = \hat{\mathbb{P}} + \tilde{\mathbb{P}}$, for $\mathbb{P} : \mathbb{A}, \mathbb{L}, \mathbb{G}, \Psi, \mathbb{D}$), therefore in the MCM itself, that is $\mathbb{C} = \hat{\mathbb{C}} + \tilde{\mathbb{C}}$. It is evident that the matrices $\mathbb{L}, \mathbb{G}$ and $\mathbb{D}$ as well as the SPV are all functions of the gain, phase and location characteristics of the array elements. This fact is exploited by the pilot calibration method proposed in this paper and described analytically in the following section.

3 CALIBRATION METHOD

The proposed calibration method is based on [4] and on the mutual coupling modelling of Section 2. To be more specific, consider an array of N sensors operating in the presence of geometrical and electrical uncertainties as well as mutual coupling effects. Based on the nominal sensor phases $\hat{\phi}$, nominal sensor locations $\hat{\underline{r}}$ and the nominal MCM $\hat{\mathbb{C}}$, the matrix

$$\mathbb{Q}_l = \hat{\mathbb{C}}^{-H} \cdot \text{diag}\{\exp(j(\hat{\phi} - \hat{\underline{r}}^T \underline{k}_l))\} \quad (5)$$

is defined. Note that the wavelength vector $\underline{k}_l$ points towards the direction (θ_l, ϕ_l) of a pilot source and that the notation 'diag{vector}' refers to a diagonal matrix.

By eliminating the noise effects from the array data covariance matrix $\mathbb{R}_{xx}$ that corresponds to the pilot source and then processing the resulting matrix with $\mathbb{Q}_l$, the matrix $\mathbb{Q}_l^H (\mathbb{R}_{xx} - \sigma^2 \mathbb{I}_N) \mathbb{Q}_l$ is formed. In this way, the majority of the terms associated with the nominal array parameters have been removed. This becomes evident, if the rank-1 matrix $\mathbb{Q}_l^H (\mathbb{R}_{xx} - \sigma^2 \mathbb{I}_N) \mathbb{Q}_l$ is rewritten as $\underline{U}_l \cdot \underline{U}_l^H$, i.e.

$$\mathbb{Q}_l^H (\mathbb{R}_{xx} - \sigma^2 \mathbb{I}_N) \mathbb{Q}_l = \underline{U}_l \cdot \underline{U}_l^H \quad (6)$$

where the vector $\underline{U}_l$ is expressed as:

$$\underline{U}_l = (\mathbb{I}_N + \hat{\mathbb{C}}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbb{C}}) \cdot \underline{\gamma} \odot \exp(j(\tilde{\phi} - \tilde{\underline{r}}^T \underline{k}_l)) \quad (7)$$

If three pilot sources are employed at three different locations and direction-independent electrical errors are assumed, the corresponding $\mathbb{Q}_l$ and $\underline{U}_l$ in Equations (5) and (7) respectively can be formed/estimated for $l = 1, 2, 3$.

It is obvious from Equation (7) that all the vectors $\underline{U}_l$ (for $l = 1, 2, 3$) feature the error part of the MCM. Nevertheless, since they include common error factors, it is expected that by dividing any two of the vectors $\underline{U}_l$ (for $l = 1, 2, 3$) element by element, the bulk of the MCM uncertainties will be filtered out. Indeed, simulation studies show that the uncertainties in the MCM knowledge, particularly of the parameters not included in the SPV model, do not degrade substantially the calibration precision. This is due to the small values of a'_i and a_i in practice. For instance, even if the power dissipated by the i^{th} sensor is nominally 10% of the directly received signal's power, a 10% deviation will only cause a 0.5% error in the knowledge of the (i, i) element of $\mathbb{A}$. On the other hand, the errors in ψ_i constitute a more important degradation factor. Yet, if the deviation from their respective nominal values is only a few degrees, as assumed in this paper, their impact can also be ignored.

It is important, however, to point out that the elementwise division involving the vectors $\underline{U}_l$ (for $l = 1, 2, 3$) cannot cancel completely the effect of the factor $\hat{\mathbb{C}}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbb{C}}$ in Equation (7). Therefore, after practically ignoring the remaining mutual coupling effects at this point, all computed error parameters will, in general, deviate slightly from the true error characteristics. In the following, the computed error

parameters are characterized by the subscript c to distinguish them from the true error values.

In these terms, for the errors in the geometrical sensor characteristics, it can be shown using Equation (7) that:

$$\mathbb{K} \cdot \underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_c = \mathbb{U} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{with } \begin{cases} \mathbb{K} = [k_1 - k_2, k_1 - k_3]^T \\ \mathbb{U} = -[\angle(\underline{U}_1 \oslash \underline{U}_2), \angle(\underline{U}_1 \oslash \underline{U}_3)]^T \end{cases}$$

where $\angle(\cdot)$ represents the phase of the argument and $\oslash$ denotes elementwise division.

For planar arrays with planar only location uncertainties, that is $\underline{r}_z = \underline{\tilde{r}}_z = \underline{\tilde{r}}_{cz} = \underline{0}$, the last row of $\underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_c$ can be ignored. Then, by redefining $\mathbb{K}$ as the matrix that consists only of the first two columns of $\mathbb{K}$, Equation (8) is simplified to:

$$\mathbb{K} \cdot [\underline{\tilde{r}}_{cx}, \underline{\tilde{r}}_{cy}]^T = \mathbb{U} \quad (9)$$

A unique solution to this system exists as long as $\text{rank}(\mathbb{K}) = 2$, i.e. the used pilot sources have different directions, equivalently different vectors k_l (it is implicit that the same pilot source can be used at different locations). Therefore, by taking this solution into account, it follows that:

$$\underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_c = [\underline{\tilde{r}}_{cx}, \underline{\tilde{r}}_{cy}, \underline{0}]^T = [(\mathbb{K}^{-1} \cdot \mathbb{U})^T, \underline{0}]^T \quad (10)$$

Subsequently, for the errors in the electrical sensor characteristics, it can be proved that for $l = 1, 2, 3$:

$$[\underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_{cl}, \underline{\tilde{\phi}}_{cl}] = [|\underline{U}_l| - \hat{\gamma}, \angle(\underline{U}_l) + \underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_c^T k_l] \quad (11)$$

Since the computed properties will generally be slightly different for each pilot source case, their mean values will be used, that is:

$$[\underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_c, \underline{\tilde{\phi}}_c] = \frac{1}{3} [\sum_{l=1}^3 \underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_{cl}, \sum_{l=1}^3 \underline{\tilde{\phi}}_{cl}] \quad (12)$$

The updated estimated values for the array gain, phase and location characteristics are:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \hat{\gamma} &= \hat{\gamma} + \underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_c \\ \hat{\phi} &= \hat{\phi} + \underline{\tilde{\phi}}_c \\ \hat{r} &= \hat{r} + \underline{\tilde{r}}_c \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

These values will be used to update the MCM in Equation (4). Apparently, only the MCM parameters that depend on the gain, phase and location characteristics are updated. The remaining parameters will still be considered to be the initial nominal ones, since in practice the assumed perturbations in their values will not have a very significant impact on the calibration results. In other words, the proposed calibration method is robust to uncertainties in the knowledge of these parameters.

The procedure described up to this point is to be re-used for the updated parameters, consequently a threshold criterion is needed for the termination of iterations. Note also that, as is common in calibration problems, one sensor has been considered to be the reference point and has known characteristics. Therefore, at each iteration, a normalisation of the values of $\hat{\gamma}$, $\hat{\phi}$ and $\hat{r}$ with respect to the reference

sensor characteristics is required so that the latter are always the known ones.

In summary, the proposed calibration technique is an iterative procedure that comprises the subsequent steps:

step-1: use three time-disjoint sources to form $\mathbb{R}_{xx}$, in Equation (3), for each source

step-2: find $\mathbb{Q}_l$ from Equation (5) and $\underline{U}_l$ from Equation (7)

step-3: calculate $\underline{\tilde{r}}_c$, $\underline{\tilde{\gamma}}_c$ and $\underline{\tilde{\phi}}_c$ from Equations (10)-(12)

step-4: update $\hat{\gamma}$, $\hat{\phi}$ and $\hat{r}$ using Equation (13) and normalise their values with respect to the reference sensor's characteristics

step-5: update the MCM from Equation (4) based on $\hat{\gamma}$, $\hat{\phi}$ and $\hat{r}$

step-6: repeat the previous 4 steps until a tolerance criterion for $\hat{\gamma}$, $\hat{\phi}$ and $\hat{r}$ is satisfied

Obviously, calibration with respect to single type errors is just a special case of the proposed methodology. Moreover, the described calibration technique can be extended for a 3-dimensional array by using another (or the one available) pilot source placed at a different azimuth angle from the previous ones.

4 REPRESENTATIVE EXAMPLES

The proposed calibration technique has been applied in different array configurations and error scenarios with satisfactory results. In this section, the results of two representative examples will be presented.

In the first example, an uncalibrated planar array of 8 sensors in a nominally uniform circular geometry of radius $\frac{\lambda}{2}$ has been considered. In the presence of uncertainties (not exceeding 10% of the nominal, 10° of the phase and $\frac{0.1\lambda}{2}$ of the location properties), the nominal characteristics are not the true ones.

μ_{initial}	μ_{final}	σ_{initial}	σ_{final}
0.0280	0.0044	0.0236	0.0028
0.0300	0.0047	0.0240	0.0027
0.0193	0.0038	0.0172	0.0028
0.0314	0.0039	0.0194	0.0028
0.0173	0.0038	0.0157	0.0025
0.0277	0.0035	0.0181	0.0012
0.0219	0.0038	0.0164	0.0013
0.0257	0.0040	0.0174	0.0019

Table 1 features the mean μ and the standard deviation σ of the absolute MCM error per sensor (i.e. per row) $|e_{\text{MCM}}|$, before and after applying the proposed calibration procedure. Table 2 features the errors ($\tilde{\phi}$ in degrees) in the knowledge of the geometrical and electrical array characteristics. Note

that the proposed method gives practically unchanged results after only 5 iterations.

In the second example, using the same uncertainty assumptions, an uncalibrated planar array of 7 sensors in a nominally uniform linear geometry of length $\frac{6\lambda}{2}$ has been considered. The dotted line in Figure 1 illustrates the MuSIC spectrum when the array is uncalibrated and operates in the presence of 5 uncorrelated sources at directions 26° , 51° , 89° , 107° and 141° . Nevertheless, if the array is calibrated using the proposed pilot technique, the performance of MuSIC for the same scenario can be drastically improved in terms of both accuracy and spectrum sharpness. Indeed, the solid line in Figure 1 depicts the ability of the proposed calibration method to rectify the nominal array and mutual coupling modelling and provide accurate direction estimates.

Figure 1 : MuSIC results for the uncalibrated and the calibrated array

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the array calibration problem has been addressed and a method that uses three time-disjoint pilot sources has been proposed to calibrate planar arrays of general geometry. The proposed approach deals simultaneously with geometrical, electrical and mutual coupling uncertainties. Representative examples have revealed the ability of the proposed

pilot calibration method to reduce substantially the errors in the knowledge of the true sensor characteristics.

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$\tilde{r}_{x,initial}$	$\tilde{r}_{x,final}$	$\tilde{r}_{y,initial}$	$\tilde{r}_{y,final}$	$\tilde{\gamma}_{initial}$	$\tilde{\gamma}_{final}$	$\tilde{\phi}_{initial}$	$\tilde{\phi}_{final}$
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-0.0858	-0.0029	0.0072	0.0029	-0.0824	0.0068	-9.4135	0.1285
-0.0667	-0.0011	-0.0051	0.0006	0.0830	-0.0096	0.1096	-0.1731
0.0613	0.0003	-0.0776	0.0008	0.0424	-0.0088	7.2548	-0.2266
-0.0821	0.0017	0.0421	-0.0028	0.0559	-0.0088	-0.0718	-0.2452
0.0713	-0.0005	0.0594	-0.0018	-0.0891	0.0001	7.0360	0.0190
-0.0689	-0.0004	-0.0123	-0.0023	-0.0131	-0.0104	-5.2262	0.2079
-0.0293	-0.0021	-0.0800	-0.0022	-0.0945	0.0035	-0.2124	0.4750